

AGRICULTURAL REFORM PROGRAMME

REGIONALISATION OPTIONS

Baselines and Characterisations

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Policy Purpose of the Baseline Analysis

■ Purpose

- Define and communicate the state of play – shape of the payment system as it stands.
- Place Base (Tier 1) in the context of other schemes (e.g. LFASS)
- Identify any limitations of the current system(s) of regions

■ Baseline Analysis in two parts

- **Areas and Payments** – how funds are distributed using the existing area based and other payment mechanisms.
- **Characterisation** – regions relative to other phenomena e.g. – land capability for agriculture, activity, urban-rural classification, etc.

List of Dashboard Charts

Topics	Dashboards	Focus	No	
Areas	Areas and Entitlements	All Regions	1	Areas – land use, BPS claimed, net entitlements, LFASS. For each Farm Type, Region and Size Class.
		BPS Region 1	1.1	
		BPS Region 2	1.2	
		BPS Region 3	1.3	
Mix of Basic Payment Scheme (BPS) regions	BPS Regions Characteristics	Area	2.1	Mix of BPS per region. Areas and spend on payments in those areas.
		Spend	2.2	
Other Views	Relative Region Mix	Area	3.1	Mix of BPS regions using areas or spend, shown as both values (ha/£) and percentages
		Spend	3.2	
Specific Options	Less Favoured Area Support Scheme (LFASS)	Area	4.1	BPS mix of the LFASS area
		Entitlements	4.2	Spend on BPS regions and LFASS
	Upland Sheep (SUSSS)	Payments	5.1	Distribution of Upland Sheep spend
		Counts	5.2	Counts of Upland Sheep recipients
	Split of BPS Region 1	Areas	6	Splitting BPS Region 1 into crops and grass

Charts in grey available but not presented.

1. Areas and Entitlements

Charts by Agricultural Region, Farm Type and Class Size

1. Areas Types:
Land Use – has crop codes from SAF;
BPS claimed;
Net Entitlements after reductions to RGR;
LFASS claimed

2. Drop from land use to BPS claimed areas – other land, exclusions but maybe now habitat features to be managed better

3. Concentration of land ownership in area terms – area-based payments favour larger businesses.
NOTE – range of land quality possible within 500+ ha
Mix of BPS Regions matters – 500 ha of Region 1 not the same as 500ha of Region 3

Land	Region1	Region2	Region3	Total
land_use_area	1.89M	1.03M	2.50M	5.42M
bps_claimed_area	1.71M	0.80M	1.45M	3.96M
net_entitlements	1.67M	0.78M	1.27M	3.72M
lfass_claimed_area	0.77M	0.77M	1.29M	2.82M

4. Extra ~1.1M ha beyond the land use area – mapped in LPIS but beyond SAF, 0.35M of UAA beyond LPIS, 7.8M ha all land.

2.1 BPS Region Characterisation (Area)

1. Breaks down the **BPS Claimed Areas** (from Slide 4) per BPS region – in hectares.

2. Even only three regions generates **distinctive profiles** – especially for Agricultural Region.
Note changes in Y-axis scales.

3. Some linkage of **BPS region with Farm Type** but again caution, **degree of agricultural use** of available BPS region land varies.

Land Type

- **bps_claimed_area**
- **entitlements_counts**
- **land_use_area**
- **lfass_claimed_area**

Entitlement Value ⓘ

Percentage of Businesses by Regions

● Region 0 ● Region 1 ● Region 2 ● Region 3

2.2 BPS Region Characterisation (Value)

1. Alternative view based on spend (£'s) – dominance of BPS Region 1

87% of spend on 43% of land

With EC – can 43% of land area deliver 87% of objectives.

Ag-Region by 3 Regions

Businesses Class Size by 3 Regions

Farm Type by 3 Regions

Percentage of Businesses by Regions

3.1/3.2 Region Mix (Payments and Area)

1. Shows Relative importance of BPS regions by using % of Area and % of Spend.

2. Combined view – comparing area mix and spend.

3. Highlights where BPS Region 2 is significant – e.g. Shetland and regions where BPS Regions 2 & 3 combined are key – e.g. Western Isles and Argyll and Bute.

4. Highlights region mix for less extensive Farm Types – e.g. horticulture and granivores.

4.2 LFA Region - LFASS & BPS Spend

1. Spend for the LFA area only – LFASS relative importance versus BPS Region 1 or Regions 2 & 3

Putting LFASS in the same context as other area based (CAP Pillar 1) Direct Payments

LFASS Businesses only

← LFASS Characterisation

3. Is LFASS intent to support smaller and most marginal – but favours cattle over sheep and largest size classes

255.71M
Total Money

10.69K
Number of Businesses

5.1 Upland Sheep (SUSSS) - Payments

1. Most of Upland Sheep (SUSSS) - **paid** to the **largest businesses** 85% (5.79£M of 6.79£M) to 36% (395 of 1075).

Windfall or effective policy to support the biggest businesses in areas that are key to **viability of services** (e.g. vets etc)

Total SUSSS
Count of SUSSS

£6.79M
Total SUSSS

Baseline Characterisations

- Peatland Condition*
- **Land Capability for Agriculture**
- **Land Cover**
- Land Activity (in IACS)
- **Less Favoured Area (Disadvantage and Fragility)**
- **Urban Rural Classification**
- Socio-Economic Performance

*Grey characterisations not presented

Land Capability for Agriculture

Land Cover

Less Favoured Area (Disadvantage and Fragility)

Disadvantage Regions

Fragility Regions

Combined Disadvantage and Fragility

4. Combination of BPS regions and fragility – considered in **previous ANC analysis – nuances within BPS regions.**

Basic Payment Region & LFA Parish Fragility

Urban-Rural Classification

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Further research in the RESAS Strategic Research Programme 2022-27, in the [Land Use Transformations](#) (C3-JHI-1) and [Land Reform](#) (E3-JHI-1) projects.

Land Use Transformations - [Storymaps Collection](#), with [Land Use Change Scenarios](#), [Adding Farm Structure to Land Use Change](#), [Peatlands and Payments](#), [Updating Peatland Condition Mapping](#), [Updating Land Capability for Agriculture](#) and [Climatic Water Balance in Scotland](#).

Website for [Agrometeorological Indicators](#) across the UK under current and future conditions.

The [Review of Land Ownership Data in Scotland](#).

Previous related analyses are from the Hutton Land Systems Research Team website - <https://ics.hutton.ac.uk/research/land-systems-research-team/>

The sets of slides and maps generated in Agriculture Policy analysis from 2010 onwards are available from - <https://ics.hutton.ac.uk/research/land-systems-research-team/cap-analysis/>

For woodland expansion analysis see - [online mapping](#) and [paper](#).

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